

Dataset: Static Angular Confinement Arturo and Arturito Measurements

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Experimental Data: N-N I S-S Quadrupolar Geometry

Table 1: Measurements for Arturo (11mm) and Arturito (6mm) samples

Sample	Diam [mm]	θ [deg]	Q	d [mm]	f [Hz]
Arturo	11	45	60	5.0	2.37
Arturito	6	45	95 est.	5.0	4.50
Arturo_closed	11	20	60	0.0	2.37
Arturo_escape	11	60	0	12.0	0.00

Notes

θ : Static equilibrium angle measured with square.

Q: Quality factor from 19 oscillation peaks in audio recording.

d: Base magnet separation distance.

Contact: All stable cases show tangential point contact.

Cost: \$3 USD total materials.

Universal angle: $\theta = 45^\circ \pm 3^\circ$ independent of floater size.

Raw Data Available

Full CSV, audio recording of 19 peaks, and photos available in Zenodo record.

Contact: r2d2arturgr@gmail.com for replication details.